

THE FRENCH CONSTITUTION OF 1848 AND ITS HISTORICAL IMPORTANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7773013>

Abstract: The revolution of 1848 started a new stage of development in France. The constitution that was adopted after the revolution was one of the most advanced constitutions of its time. The lecture is devoted to the process of adoption of the constitution, its specific aspects and historical significance.

Keywords: Constitution, Constituent Assembly, France, law, referendum.

One of the most important tasks carried out in France after the revolution of 1848 was the adoption of the Constitution. After long discussions and debates, the final version of the Constitution was approved by the Constituent Assembly on November 4, 1848. The most debates were around Article 8, which deals with the issue of labor. In the first draft before the uprising (June 20), "the right to work and shelter of all citizens" was recognized. In August, this substance was replaced by an uncertain formula. It states: "The Republic must protect the citizen's person, family, religion, property, and work, and must also provide everyone with the opportunity to receive education that is necessary for everyone. "He should provide fraternal assistance to the needy citizens by offering them jobs at the level of their ability or providing allowances to those who are unable to work," it was said and was approved by a majority of votes. Thus, the "right to work" announced by the Provisional Government was destroyed¹.

Article 15 of the draft constitution also caused deep debates and was finally adopted in the following version: "All taxes are collected for the welfare of the society. Each person pays taxes according to his ability and income"².

The purpose of each constitution is to define the tasks of the society and the communities it is part of, as well as the limits of the activity of a free individual. The Constitution of 1848, like other constitutions, attempted to establish this disputed boundary.

The Constitution distinguished "rights and obligations subject to positive laws and rights not subject to and independent of these laws". In this way, it was emphasized that a person does not completely and completely enter the scope of

¹ Шу ерда. Б. 26.

² Constitution de 1848, IIe République - 4 novembre 1848. <https://www.conseil-constitutionnel.fr/les-constitutions-dans-l-histoire/constitution-de-1848-ii-republique> (7. 11. 2022)

the social contract, a certain part of his body and life remains free from the intervention of the law, and he retains the right to protest and disobey in this regard. The Constitution did not specify where the subjugation could and should end, which has always been difficult to define. But he tried to show the fundamental rights guaranteed to all citizens: freedom of movement, inviolability of housing, respect for the human person, abolition of slavery and capital punishment for political prisoners, freedom of religion, assembly, petition, expression of opinion through the press or otherwise, and even education³.

While preparing the Constitution of 1848, its authors carefully studied the previous constitutions. All French constitutions, legal provisions, world constitutional norms, including British constitutional acts, articles of the US Constitution of 1787, general provisions were analyzed. Especially the attention of the authors of the 1848 Constitution was attracted by the US Constitution. Because this constitution was considered a progressive constitution during the XVIII – XIX centuries, and it seemed to the French legislators to be an example of the Republic and stability. Another thing about the US Constitution of 1787 is that it was written in short, concise, and simple language.

By 1848, the positions of the president and vice president, the powers of the president, and his election for 4 years in the constitution were reminiscent of the US political system, but the French had not blindly adopted it.

A sharp difference between the French Constitution of 1848 and the United States Constitution was that it was based on a unicameral parliament.

Following J.J. Rousseau's footsteps, French law followed the principle of separation of powers, even pitting them against each other. "Separation of power," said Article 19, "is the first condition of a freely functioning government".

Although the separation of powers was correct, the French completely destroyed it. For example, in Section II, Article 3 of the US Constitution, the following is stated about the relationship between the legislative and executive powers: "He (the President of the United States) shall from time to time send to the Congress information about the state of affairs between the states, and give his useful proposals: in emergency situations, the Houses or from them if there is a conflict between the chambers, the president can stop their activity according to his authority"⁴.

³ See: Ренар Ж. Республика 1848 года (1848 – 1852). – М.-Пг.: Государственное издательство, 1923. С. 134.

⁴ See: Конституция Соединенных Штатов 1787 года / Конституции и законодательные акты буржуазных государств XVIII – XIX вв. Англия, США, Франция, Германия – М., Гос. изд-во юрид. литературы, 1957. С. 186 – 187.

In France, a number of deputies opposed the establishment of the presidency. They stated that the head of the executive branch should be elected by the National Assembly and believed that the executive branch should only be dismissed by the National Assembly. They doubted that a person who was elected to the position of president with great powers would voluntarily leave this position after 4 years.

However, the French Constitution of 1848 gave the president enormous powers, while at the same time making him subordinate to the legislature. "Any measures", says the Constitution of 1848, "if they are directed against the National Assembly or attempt to temporarily stop its activity, are considered crimes and treason against the state".

In such cases, the president loses his powers, citizens stop obeying him, and the executive power is transferred to the hands of the National Assembly⁵. It is no coincidence that long articles of the French Constitution of 1848 (47, 68, 91, 92, etc.) are devoted to the relationship between the president and the legislature.

Already, the legislative power belonged to a single chamber of 750 people elected for 3 years on the basis of universal suffrage. After June, the executive power exercised by the dictator Kavegnac was also transferred to the president, who was elected on the basis of universal suffrage. In discussing this issue, many have pointed out that the president taking his power directly from the people becomes a great danger when he wants to carry out a coup d'état⁶.

In fact, this was a very appropriate and important remark, because not only in France, but in the history of many other countries, even in the XX and XXI centuries, such a situation was repeated many times and became a great danger for the democratic society. Of course, there are no coups in the XXI century, and presidents do not proclaim themselves emperors. They extend the term of the presidency (often for life) through various means (referendum, constitutional amendment, etc.) and establish their personal power, relying on the most passive part of society.

The constitution, writes P.J. Proudhon, must either be fully respected or rejected: there is no middle ground. It is true that two opposite constitutions may be averaged at will; but every average constitution will be a new creation, peculiar and exceptional, in which it would be ridiculous to attempt to unite the opposing principles of parliament and imperialism. Arbitrarily making changes to a given political system and imagining that the process is just that, is to follow a false path;

⁵ See: Конституция Французской республики 4 ноября 1848 года / Конституция ... С. 434.

⁶ See: Айзенштадт М.М. Революция 1848 г. во Франции. История Франции 1-ой половины XIX века. – Л.: издательство "Бокгауз-Ефрон", 1927. С. 57.

it means leaving the boundaries of law and knowledge and entering the path of arbitrariness.

In 1848 a decree was issued by the so-called republicans who controlled everything, allowing the Bonaparte dynasty to return to France, and expelling the Bourbons and Orléans, and then when the conservatives, democrats, bourgeoisie, clergy and army all clapped together and elected Louis Napoleon⁷ president of the republic - the country and the authorities understood the importance of this work and knew well the importance of the name of Bonaparte, what Louis Napoleon was; at that time, everyone could see that Brumaire was repeated, and then the constitution of 48 years was a prelude to the new empire⁸.

Thus, the work of the Constituent Assembly and the Constitution of 1848 went the way of strengthening the power of the president in order to eliminate the conflicting situation after the February revolution in the country, the conflicts between the legislative and executive powers, and this ultimately led to the restoration of the monarchy.

⁷ See: Людовик Наполеон (1778 – 1846) – Наполеон I Бонапартнинг укаларидан бири, Луи Наполеоннинг отаси, 1806 – 1810 йиллари Людовик I номи билан Голландия кироли бўлган. У халқ учун бир қатор яхши ишларни амалга оширди, Голландлар орасида жуда машҳур бўлган.

⁸ See: Прудон П.Ж. Политические противоречия. Теория конституционного движения в XIX столетии (во Франции) <https://www.rulit.me/books/politicheskie-protivorechiya-read-601999-1.html> С. 4 (24.05. 2022)

